

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B285
Date: 19 April 2007
Take Off 21:50:11 00:27:24
Landing: 22:42:13 05:44:08
Flight Time 0h52m02 5h16m44

Campaign: IASI - ARIES

Operating Area: Ellington - Oklahoma

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Stuart Newman	Met Office
5	Flight Manager	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Paul James	FAAM
7	AVAPS	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	ARIES	Joss Kent	Met Office
10	MARSS / Wet Nephelometer	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
11	AMS	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
12	Chemistry / CCM2	Bob Wells	FAAM
13	Mission Scientist 2	Alessio Bozzo	University of Bologna
14	Mission Scientist 3	Jon Taylor	Met Office
15			
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Flight Track:

B285 Track 19-APR-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B285
 Date: 19-20/4/07
 Project: IASI
 Location: Gulf of Mexico

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
213716		Start-Up	0.05 kft	359	29'36.06N 95'10.06W
214540		ASP	0.05 kft	358	
215011		T/O	0.04 kft	179	
224213		Land	0.01 kft	104	New Orleans
224344		ASP	0.03 kft	031	
002713		ASP	1.8 kft	200	002007
002724		T/O	2.4 kft	195	002527
005527	013528	Run 1.1	0.92 - 0.94 kft	158	
014009	021849	Run 1.2	0.95 - 0.93 kft	334	1000ft S to A
021849	022002	Profile 1	0.93 - 1.9 kft	338	2000ft
022329	025335	Profile 1.2	1.9 - 30.1 kft	135	
025634	030136	Profile 1.3	30.1 - 33.0 kft	352	
030136	032330	Run 2.1	33.0 kft	330	
030148		Sonde 1	33.0 kft	328	
030404		Sonde 2	33.0 kft	322	
030701		Sonde 3	33.0 kft	322	
030901		Sonde 4	33.0 kft	329	
031059		Event	33.0 kft	330	Sat overpass 03:11
031527		Sonde 5	33.0 kft	329	
031732		Sonde 6	33.0 kft	329	
032050		Sonde 7	33.0 kft	329	
032832	035250	Run 2.2	33.0 kft	149	
033113		Sonde 8	33.0 kft	165	
033505		Sonde 9	33.0 kft	165	
033902		Sonde 10	33.0 kft	164	
034314		Sonde 11	33.0 kft	164	164 dropped
034314					
034700		Sonde 12	33.0 kft	164	
035549	042559	Profile 2	33.0 - 0.89 kft	315	
042600	043131	Run 3	0.87 - 0.88 kft	338	
054408		Land	-.01 kft	245	
054530		ASP	-.01 kft	270	
054933		Shutdown	-.01 kft	359	29'36.08N 95'10.06W

B285 Track 19-APR-07

Sortie Brief Eastern Gulf of Mexico

Flight B285

Thurs 19th April 2007

Mission Scientist: Stuart Newman

Briefing: 1445L 1945Z

Take off: 1645L 2145Z

Final landing: approximately 0200L

Satellite overpass 03:11Z

Aim: To underfly IASI on the Metop satellite in the Eastern Gulf of Mexico along the sub satellite track.

Location: Eastern Gulf of Mexico.

Weather conditions: Clear skies or broken clouds.

Key instruments: ARIES, MARSS, AVAPS, Core Chem, Cloud Phys

Fixed Points: BAe 146 to follow fixed ground positions as follows:

Over GULF of MEXICO following jetway between IVONE and ELIOM

Fixed point A: (28° 00.00' N, 89° 05.00' W) = just south of IVONE

Fixed point B: (25° 03.46' N, 87° 41.03' W) = ELIOM

1. Take off from Houston and transit to New Orleans for first refuel (45 mins)
2. Refuel stop (90 mins)
3. Take off from New Orleans and transit to point A to arrive at 1000 ft (20 mins)
4. SLR from A to B at 1000ft (50mins)
5. SLR from B to A at 1000ft (50mins)
6. Profile from A to B from 1000ft to FL350 then continue on to B at FL350 (50 mins)
7. SLR from B to A at FL350 (35mins) Overpass occurs in middle of this run at 0311Z
8. SLR from A to B at FL350 (35mins)
9. Profile from B towards A from FL350 to 1000ft continuing to A at 1000ft (50mins)
10. Transit back to New Orleans (20 mins)
11. Land at New Orleans (flight time 310 mins; total elapsed so far 445 mins)
12. Refuel stop (60 mins)
13. Transit back to Houston (45 mins)
14. Land at Houston approx. 0155L (flight time 45 mins; total elapsed time 550 mins)

Special notes for dropsonde launches: aim is to launch sondes with good coverage along the sub-satellite track but with particular density at the overpass time. Approximate timings for 14 dropsondes if sondes take 16 mins or less to fall:

Assume Run 2.1 begins at 0250Z

		<i>Time (Z)</i>	<i>Time relative to overpass (mins)</i>
Dropsonde	#1	0251	T-20
	#2	0253	T-18
	#3	0301	T-10
	#4	0304	T-7
	#5	0307	T-4
	#6	0309	T-2
	#7	0317	T+6
	#8	0320	T+9
	#9	0323	T+12

Assume Run 2.2 begins at 0328Z

#10	0330	T+19
#11	0337	T+26
#12	0345	T+34
#13	0353	T+42
#14	0400	T+49

Mission scientist's debrief for JAIVEx flight B285 on 19 April 2007

S. M. Newman

Summary:

Night time sortie over Gulf of Mexico under MetOp with WB-57 also flying
Partially cloudy conditions were observed, with mid-level and cirrus clouds in area
Unusual profiles showed extremely moist but unsaturated upper troposphere
Some clear scenes were observed, but many will be contaminated by clouds

This was a planned clear sky night time sortie under MetOp with WB-57 over the Gulf of Mexico. It was immediately apparent on transit to New Orleans for a preliminary refuel that high-level cirrus clouds were present over the Gulf. There was a hitch with power outage when the GPU failed, which delayed take-off by 20 minutes and affected the AMS performance. Consequently the sortie was foreshortened and a second refuel at New Orleans at the end of science was not required.

With take-off and transit to the operating area at dusk low- and mid-level cloud was observed, though it was patchy – these will have contaminated the IASI fields of view from MetOp, but the sortie should still be an interesting case of a satellite overpass in varying cloud fraction conditions. Two low level runs at 1000 feet were executed at the beginning; ARIES viewed in the nadir during the first and zenith during the second which characterised both the SST (strong gradients near the coast) and the varying upper cloud amounts (less at the northern end of the run as deduced from ARIES brightness temperatures and eagle-eyed observers). A profile climb to FL330 was managed, which an extremely moist upper troposphere measured but no actual cloud particles seen until maximum altitude was reached. Two runs were performed at FL330, the first coinciding with the MetOp overpass. Seven then five sondes were released during the two runs, spaced at intervals to achieve good spatial coverage. ARIES monitored the cirrus signal at times during the zenith views at high level – some clear patches were deduced. Some of the high level runs were conducted in cloud, with 2D probes showing small ice aggregates and occasionally more pristine habits. The dropsondes and in situ data showed a moist layer above 400 mb but with a much drier airmass in the mid-troposphere; there were unusual persistent thin moisture features at lower levels in all soundings. The WB-57 operated at FL550 along the same track as the FAAM 146, and the dataset should be interesting to test retrieval schemes in the presence of clouds.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

MISSION SCIENTIST : STUART NEWMAN

JAI VEX GULF OF MEXICO

Flight No **B.285**.....

Date **19/4/2007**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
215011	TAKE-OFF				Transit to New Orleans prelim. refuel
2258					In transit considerable high level cloud
2300		FL185↑			Some marine Cu fields
2305		FL210			Just below cloud base at this point
2309		"			Cloud base much higher, thin bands Ci, clear below
2315					2D reports low PCASP aerosol on ascent
2333		5600' ↓			On approach, clear at all levels below but thin Ci persists above
2342	LAND NEW ORLEANS				Science power interrupted so AMS compromised (vacuum)
002527	TAKE-OFF				13 minutes behind sortie schedule
0028		4600' ↑			Thin but extensive high cloud PCASP 2000 on ascent but dropping at higher level
0041		FL110	160	28°48' / 89°36'	reasonably clear above here, more high level cloud ahead Clear below (rigs, shipping lights)
0051		FL3500 ↓	097	28°06' / 89°06'	PCASP 700 shot up from 90
0054		1250' ↓	151		PCASP 1400
005527	R1.1	1000'	153	27°54' / 89°00'	Very dark, appears cirrus on horizon
0100	"	"	155	27°36' / 88°54'	T = 19.6°C, Td = 14°C, wind 3ms ⁻¹ / 27°
0107	"	"	154	27°12' / 88°42'	Heiman on this run 22.5°C ↑ 24°C Strong gradients in SST away from coast
0115					Captain notices cloud above which is not high, thinks Stratiform patches
0130					Upper pyraeometer not very informative on what is above unfortunately
013528	end R1.1	1000'		25°42' / 88°W	Extremely bad comms here

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.285**.....

 Date **19/4/07**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
014009	R1.2	1000'	334	25°42'/88°W	Revised 25° ... 88 0.47W
0141					Clear above says Jan
014156					Underpatch of cloud briefly
014220	"	"			Upper cloud (low/med.) 288K ARIES
0144					55,000 ft WB-57 50 miles from southern pt heading north too
014550	"	"	340	26°/88°6'	~3000ft low level cloud?
014637					Clear above, cloudy at intervals
014750					Clear now above 220K window ARIES
0150					ARIES BTs imply perhaps 2 levels low/mid-level cloud and maybe high cloud assoc. 220 K.
015210					ARIES: clear above
0158					Ci signature for time in ARIES
"	"	1000'	339	26°45'/88°30'	More Ci at this end
0202					Ci above
0203					Bit water cloud inferred from ARIES, has been mainly cirrus
0210	"	"	338	27°24'/88°45'	ARIES reports clear above, visually (looking at moon + stars) seems quite clear.
0212	"	"	223	27°30'/88°54'	Still clear; steep dip in Heilmann SST
0215					Five minutes of clear ARIES spectra 27.5°N northwards
021849	End R1.2 Start P1	1000' ↑	337	27°54'/89°W	
022002	interr- upt	2000'			
022329	P1.2	2000' ↑	142		

↓
 2-
 2500
 Cloud
 base
 on
 TCh

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.285**
 FAAM © 2004

 Date **19/4/07**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
0234					Dip in O ₃ profile on ascent reported
0241	P1.2↑	FL220↑	166	26°42'/88°24'	T/φ gran shows moist layer ~ FL220
0245	"	FL255	165		T = -21.6°C T _d = -28.3°C Wind 25ms ⁻¹ 257°
0248					"Both sides clear as a whistle" despite moist profile
025335		FL300	182	25°49'/88°0'	
0255					v. few & ice crystals reported 2D
025634	P1.3	FL300↑	352		
03036	R2.1	FL330	328	26°12'/88°6'	dropsonde 030148 2D few crystals aggregates max size 200µm
					dropsonde 030404 launch
					030701
030835					small aggregates
					dropsonde 030901 — no cirrus
0313					NASA just crossed climb point
					dropsonde 031527 FUVS working!
					dropsonde 031732 ARIES looks clear below
031930					Can see lights below, looks clear
					dropsonde 032050
032240					Suggestion from ARIES spectra of thin Ci above
032330	end R2.1	FL330		28°0'/89°W	
032549					In cirrus; 2D cones 20-40 200µm
0327	in turn				Columns seen — max size 250-300µm cones ~ 30
032832	R2.2	FL330	172	27°54'/89°W	ARIES showing thin Ci above
					dropsonde 033113 ARIES clear below

height
 7000'
 12500'
 21,000'
 27200'

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B285 **T/O:** 002724
Date of flight: 20/4/07 **Land:** 054408

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B285 **T/O:** 002724
Date of flight: 20/4/07 **Land:** 054408

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y Y	
4) Log on to FLOODS	Y	
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B285.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 218437
6) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE	Y	Blocks read =50377
a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B285.dat	Y	Blocks written = 50377
b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B285_seadas.dat	Y	Bad reads =0
WAVE> exit	Y	
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE	Y	
a) Default directory: PMSDATA:	Y	
b) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B285_seadas.dat	Y	
d) Comment string:	Y	
e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i>	Y	Start = 0
f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i>	Y	End = 240000
g) Read 2DC: Y	Y	Ignore error message scroll
h) Read 2DP: Y	Y	(vestigial error from tapes)
i) Secondary data: Y	Y	
j) FSP-SYNC: Y	Y	Are FRW, FSP, IMB,
k) cmd.str: Y	Y	PCA,SEC
l) Auto time correction: N	Y	files in PMSDATA?
m) Full length secondary: N	Y	Are they non-zero in size?
8) FLOODS> WAVE	Y	2D image display and printing
i). WAVE> imagedisplay	Y	Must be done from FLOODS
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:	Y	itself.
b) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	
c) Time from IWC plot: N	Y	
d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP	Y	
e) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i>	Y	
f) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i>	Y	
g) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images)	Y	Note any problems with
ii). WAVE> auto_image	Y	images
a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA:	Y	Prepare imagery for Core data
b) Flight number: Bnnn	Y	From own PC again
c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD	Y	
d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i>	Y	Start =
e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i>	Y	End =
f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10	Y	
iii). WAVE> exit to create files	Y	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_
iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC	Yes no	Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps
v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter	2dp noise	Notes on this in instructions
vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>	NO	<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X =</p> <p>Start = 002720 End = 054500</p> <p>Time data processed to = 052406 2dproc files present? yes No output generated!!!</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>	no	<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records =</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>	no	<p>X = Y = (X+1)</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>	no	Correlated?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number: B285****T/O: 002724****Date of flight: 20/4/07****Land: 054408**

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	yes	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	yes	Min size =2 Vol flow rate = 0.8
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5 , 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	yes	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	No	Times don't match X = Y = X+1 =
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and NEPH peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph total blue scatter</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	no	Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B285	Date	19-20 Apr 2007 (sondes launched on 20 th , Z time)
Page No.	1 of 2	Operator	Doug Anderson

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
03:01:48	1	Launch	261.50 -41.90 91.85 279.30 29.60 -20.90 -88.167600 26.226500
03:14:01	1	land	1013.29 23.53 999.00 73.03 5.44 - 10.86 -88.090628 26.194562
03:04:06	2	Launch	261.50 -41.80 96.87 284.40 28.40 -18.50 -88.272200 26.398900 10069.40
03:16:09	2	land	1013.59 23.50 60.06 68.58 4.98 - 11.35 -88.193147 26.366820
03:07:03	3	Launch	261.60 -42.10 80.71 287.50 28.30 -17.10 -88.421400 26.630300 10068.20
03:19:21	3	land	1013.35 23.61 56.35 52.60 5.66 - 11.30 -88.339792 26.595119 slightly late winds CH3
03:09:03	4	Launch	261.50 -41.90 64.92 289.00 30.70 -16.00 -88.505600 26.807400 10069.40
03:21:11	4	land	1012.61 23.44 54.76 85.79 3.98 - 10.43 -88.424009 26.770649
03:16:00	5	Launch	261.60 -42.00 79.00 292.20 32.00 -17.60 -88.796100 27.409400 10066.90
03:27:11	5	land	1013.05 23.00 59.15 78.47 3.91 - 11.08 -88.695800 27.330189
03:17:33	6	Launch	261.70 -42.30 97.89 294.90 32.50 -17.70 -88.858000 27.537000 10065.70
03:29:29	6	land	1013.71 22.49 999.00 31.84 4.01 - 11.07 -88.773044 27.499046
03:20:51	7	Launch	261.80 -42.40 91.81 296.40 33.40 -17.90 -88.987100 27.803400 10064.10
03:33:10	7	land	9999.00 99.00 999.00 37.14 3.95 - 11.30 -88.896288 27.762885 CH3 Weak telemetry
03:31:15	8	Launch	261.50 -42.50 78.05 279.00 28.80 -18.40 -88.967000 27.762600 10069.40
03:43:19	8	land	1013.98 22.09 61.77 35.94 2.94 - 11.33 -88.879069 27.722810
03:35:06	9	Launch	261.60 -42.20 82.46 265.70 29.00 -16.70 -88.788200 27.393500 10066. CH1 wea telemetry at height
03:47:10	9	land	1013.62 22.82 62.48 52.56 4.19 - 11.85 -88.700779 27.352760
03:39:03	10	Launch	261.60 -42.40 92.80 262.30 25.70 -16.50 -88.602200 27.006700 10068.20
03:50:49	10	land	9999.00 99.00 999.00 46.63 3.89 - 11.51 -88.521115 26.970914

B285 CVI log

4/19/07 9:13:13 PM Hygrometer zero @ 16:12
4/19/07 10:02:09 PM Hygrometer zero @ 16:12
4/19/07 10:02:11 PM Hygrometer zero @ 16:12
4/19/07 10:02:25 PM 220156 zero
4/19/07 2:29:35 PM 022900 lyman zero
4/19/07 3:25:22 PM 03245900 lyman zero
4/19/07 4:58:17 PM 045738 lyman zero

ARIES flight log

Flight: B285

page 1 of

Date: 19/04/07

Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: IASI HOUSTON - Ecorem Gulf of Mexico

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
21:52			housekeeping				
22145	Transit	1/60	cal	clsd	7069	3076	
22170	Transit						
0:15:15			Resurveyed housekeeping after loss of power on				
			refuel				
0:46:30	Transit	1/60	clsd	cal	7082	3165	No good for disturbance disturbance
05529	R1-1	1/60	cal	clsd	7088	3160	
05641	R1-1	600/1	None	clsd	7094	3036	Smear Nocturnal - No good!
05742	un	600/1	None	clsd	7094	3102	
010258	R1-1	1/60	cal	clsd	7099	3097	
010349	R1-1	600/1	None	clsd	7107	3088	Smear at run
010850	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7079	3116	cal.
011007	un	600/1	None	clsd	7110	3090	Smear run
011508	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7086	3087	cal
011619	un	600/1	None	clsd	7098	3107	Smear run
012124	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7084	3102	cal.
012280	un	600/1	None	clsd	7102	3119	Smear Noct. M
012733	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7085	3117	cal.
012856	un	600/1	None	clsd	7090	3169	Smear noct. M
013383		1/60	cal	clsd	7112	3142	
013747	R1-2	1/60	cal	clsd	7086	3163	
013910	un	600/1	Zen	open	7077	3282	7077 3341
014110	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7077	3375	
014520	un	600/1	Zen	open	7077	3444	
015030	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7048	3531	cal.
015145	un	600/1	Zen	open	7044	3546	
015648	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7044	3711	cal.
015800	un	600/1	Zen	open	7044	3988	Errors above
20308	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7039	3919	7-3
020422	un	600/1	Zen	open	7018	3906	
020927	un	1/60	cal	clsd	7063	4000	cal

ARIES flight log

Flight: B286

page 2 of

Date: 20/04/07 Operator(s): Joss

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes:

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
021045	R1-2	600/1	Zen open		7047	4008	Clear above.
021548	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7053	4087	
021656	R2-2	600/1	Zen open		7055	4086	Clear above - end nearly.
021859	R1-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	7099	4064	
022401	Profile		Prof	start of			Profile ZHCNCHZ - Dec.
022400	Profile		Cal	clsd	6999	3090	Cal in profile on ramp
022632	Profile		Prof				Profile ZHCNCHZ - Dec.
030137	R2-1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7039	3076	Cal @ min start
030255	R2-1	600/1	Nad	clsd	7075	3053	Nad or Swans - ended quarter was
030745	R2-1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7087	3073	Cal
030905	R2-1	600/1	Nad	clsd	7148	3070	Nad or
031107	R2-1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7076	3072	Cal
031523	R2-1	600/1	Nad	clsd	7076	3058	Nad or Swans - started script in error!
031823	R2-1	300/1	Nad	clsd	7076	3084	Cal
032008	R2-1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7090	3026	Cal
032130	R2-1	180/1	Zen open		7011	2978	Zen then cirrus above
032319	R2-1	1/60	Cal	clsd	7065	3070	Cal
032722	R2-2	1/60	Cal	clsd	6961	3107	Start in turn
032845	R2-2	300/1	Zen open		7048	3062	Zen view - some swans
033123	R2-2	300/1	Nad	clsd	7098	3058	Nad clear below
033356	n n	1/60	Cal	clsd	7067	3008	Cal
033510	n n	300/1	Zen open		7023	3067	Small Cirrus above - clear at end
033745	n n	300/1	Nad	clsd	7097	3095	Clear below - script started in error!
033745	n n	1/60	Cal	clsd	7083	3052	Cal
034156	n n	1/60	Cal	clsd	7095	3050	Cal
034305	n n	300/1	Zen open		7011	3117	Purely Cirrus above
034510	n n	300/1	Nad	clsd	7109	3013	Clear below.
034826	n n	1/60	Cal	open	7082	3085	Cal
034945	n n	300/1	Zen open		7057	3060	Zen
035229	n n	300/1	Nad				
035301	n n	1/60	Cal	clsd	7082	3068	@ end of run

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	19/04/07	Flight	B285	log pages
Operator(s)	Chawn Harlow		Campaign	JIAVEX		
Departure	Ellington etd 2145		Arrival	Ellington eta 0700+2400		

**System start
MARSS**

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on			at time	2030 ish		
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	°C	Ch	°C	Ch18	°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C	17	58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on			at time			
Initial target temperatures	Hot	311	Cold	311		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)			at time	2030 ish		
Scan indication		Monitor	•		Visual	•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	Deimos not operated				
Turn on Deimos CPU					
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***					
Start Deimos Software			at time		
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold		
Target heating					
Scan indication		Monitor		Visual	
Weather	Cloud		Precip		
	Surface		Pressure		
	Other				

System functionality check (after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	2	at time	21:20:22	
Brightness temps 'sensible'					•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	344.7	Cold	311
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B	
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)	
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)
	31.8	32.2	37.7	40.1	39.0

Power changeover

Headset on before start					•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.				•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)					•
Exit Deimos Software (x)					
POWER CHANGEOVER					
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton				•
Restart Deimos Software					
System running again			at time	21:42:44	

Flight:

B285

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nezvorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 26/06/2007
15:34:46

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

20/04/2007 17:40:57

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B285

Date: 19 April 2007

Instruments

1. GPU failure at New Orleans
2. CGPS unable to connect

Aircraft

Nil

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 19/04/07

Flight No: B285

Pre-Flighter: JT / BW

Item	√ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	N/A
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	DRIER CHANGED, O ₂ CALIB
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nezovorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	SEE ABOVE
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	" "
17	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	JK FIXING PUMP
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			

External Checks overleaf →

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> ✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	BW
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	"
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			<u>Signed</u>
43	<input type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/> IGEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

New plot, same times

Flight B285 03:32:46

Heading 166 deg Speed 359 knots Height 33.0kft Press 261mb

Lat 27°30.0'N Long 88°54.0'W Wind 29 ms-1/ 273 deg

Temp -42.35C Dewpoint -42.51C

From start to now

Current values
 TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 12765 secs
 HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP 15.74 deg C

✓ ~~Joss = 1251-1236~~
 ✓ ~~Chawn = 1240-1232~~
 ✓ ~~Gaynor = 1237~~
 ✓ ~~Joe = 1241~~
 ✓ ~~Atago = 1235~~
 ✓ Bob. - 1259
 ? ~~and W - 1252~~
 ✓ ~~JF = 1276~~
 ✓ Ruth.
 1244
 Dave 12.45

O 44
 O 5
 Ryan
 Playe

New plot, same times

Flight B285 22:13:57

Heading 87 deg Speed 329 knots Height 21.0kft Press 445mb

Lat 29°12.0'N Long 92°48.0'W Wind 19 ms-1/ 261 deg

Temp -15.72C Dewpoint -16.89C

From 21:41:24 to now

Current values			
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	80037	secs	● All
HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP	16.07	deg C	○

New plot, same times

Flight B285 01:45:10

Heading 339 deg Speed 222 knots Height 0.9kft Press 979mb

Lat 26°0.0'N Long 88°6.0'W Wind 6 ms-1/ 56 deg

Temp 20.94C Dewpoint 15.77C

From start to now

Current values
TIME FROM MIDNIGHT 6309 secs © All
HEIMAN SURFACE TEMP 24.3 deg C C

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B285:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP	Not operated on this flight
FWVS	No log is taken for this FWVS
AMS	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	31 Aug 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight

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